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INTRODUCTION

Dear Conference Participants,

As the Chairman of the Organising Committee it gives me a great pleasure to welcome you to the **Supercomputing Frontiers 2016** in Singapore.

We have worked hard to create an exciting and intriguing conference program. We aspired to bring the luminaries of Supercomputing and thinkers who shape the future of technology and who influence our own way of thinking and expand our understanding.

The first edition of this conference, in 2015, brought together some of the most prominent supercomputer architects who have built outstanding systems: Alan Gara who designed BlueGene line of supercomputers; Thomas Sterling who built "The Beowulf," the first cluster computer; and Satoshi Matsuoka, the architect of Tsubame line of Supercomputers, among others.

This year we will have the opportunity to listen to the creators of processors and supercomputers that are just being conceived or in early testing stages or not quite built yet, such as REX Computing processor, Neuromorphic processor from TrueNorth program, Quantum Annealer from D-Wave, Automata Processor from Micron and Design principles for the US Department of Energy Exascale program which will serve as a blueprint to build the most powerful supercomputers in the USA.

We will explore the continuum between a human brain and a brain in silicon, the medium of communicating between a human and a supercomputer, and special languages to program them. A separate session will be devoted to data storage and new file systems required for the Exascale era.

And of course, we will have the entire assortment of talks on the important scientific problems that are only possible to be solved with the power of supercomputers.

We hope that the guests who joined our optional tour of some of the most interesting research facilities in Singapore would be rightly impressed with the quality of research facilities and the breadth of fascinating research problems being pursued here.

This conference is also an excellent opportunity for our Singaporean computing fraternity to bond together and to get acquainted with the world leaders who visit us on such an occasion. The eleven workshops that are offered on Friday will give more chances to deepen their expertise.

We hope that the scientific program of **Supercomputing Frontiers 2016**, the tour, workshops, the networking and the conference dinner will leave our participants with new creative ideas and pleasant memories. Please enjoy the conference and come back again in 2017!

Yours Sincerely,

Dr. Marek Michalewicz
Program Chair, Supercomputing Frontiers 2016

Co-Chairs:

Marek T. MICHALEWICZ, A*STAR Computational Resource Centre
HE Bing Sheng, Nanyang Technological University
WONG Weng Fai, National University of Singapore

Committee Members:

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John KAN, A*STAR
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Computational
Resource Centre

Agency for
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and Research

Programme Chair:

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William HARROD, Department of Energy, USA

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David KAHANER, ATIP, USA

Scott KLASKY, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, USA

Michael KRAJECKI, University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne, France

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Madhav MARATHE, Virginia Bioinformatics Institute, Virginia Tech, USA

Satoshi MATSUOKA, Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan

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TAN Tin Wee, National Supercomputing Centre Singapore

John A. TAYLOR, CSIRO, Australia

Vladimir VOEVODIN, Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia

Biopolis: Matrix Building, Levels 4

30 Biopolis Street, Singapore 138671 (Nearest MRT Station: Buona Vista MRT)

By Mass Rapid Transit (MRT) train:

Commuter may take the East-West (Green) train line or the Circle line (Yellow) and alight at Buona Vista MRT Station (E21). The walk from the station to Biopolis takes approximately 10 – 15 minutes.

By Taxi:

Taxis can be hailed at various taxi stands, along major roads or by booking a taxi. All taxi fares are metered and are based on a flag down rate and the distance travelled. Additional surcharges will apply during the morning and evening peak hour times.

By Public Bus:

Public bus services operating along North Buona Vista Road include 91, 92, 95, 74, 191, 196, 198, 200. You can take these buses and alight along North Buona Vista Road and walk up to Biopolis.

By Car:

From North Buona Vista Road, turn right into North Buona Vista Drive. Please use Car Park Entrance A and park your vehicle in the public car park at Basement 3. The Orange Zone is the closest parking zone for Matrix building. Follow the signs to “To Matrix Lift Lobby” and locate Lift D. Take Lift D to Lobby at Level 1. At Matrix Level 1, please use either the escalator or passenger lifts to the Conference Auditorium at Level 4.

GENERAL INFORMATION

REGISTRATION INFORMATION

The welcome/registration desk is located on the 4th floor of the Matrix Building where the conference will be held. Registration is open from 8:00am daily where you may check in and collect your registration badge. On-site registration will also be available.

BADGES & PASSES

A name badge is provided with your registration documents upon arrival at the Welcome/Registration Desk in the Matrix. For security and regulation purposes, the wearing of the badge is compulsory at all times inside the Matrix. Only persons wearing a "SCF2016" badge are entitled to attend the main conference programme, workshops, lunches & breaks. Badges will have icons depicting your exclusive access to the conference dinner and research labs tour.

KEY PROGRAMME DATES

Monday	14 March	Exclusive research labs tour (pre-registration is required)
Tuesday - Thursday	15 - 17 March	Main conference programme
Wednesday	16 March	Conference Dinner (pre-registration is required)
Friday	18 March	Workshops

INTERNET ACCESS

Free wifi internet access is available at the conference venue.

The network name is: **BIOPOLIS SHARED FACILITIES**. There is no password to access it.

SPEAKERS' INFORMATION

The auditorium is equipped with a projector and laptop. Speakers are requested to upload their presentations to the venue's laptop at least **TWO HOURS** before their session starts. Personal laptops may also be used. In any case, a copy of the presentation is requested by the A*CRC Committee. The laptops provided are equipped with Microsoft Windows 7, Office 2010 (PowerPoint, Word & Excel), Adobe Reader, Windows Media Player and VLC Video Player. A Mac laptop will also be available. Technical assistance will be available at all times.

MEAL BREAKS

All tea breaks and lunches will be served in the main foyer of Level 4 of The Matrix. Please refer to your programme schedule for the meal periods.

Hindu vegetarian meals are available upon request. Please check in with the staff at the registration table if you would like to make a request for a vegetarian meal.

BEVERAGES

Freshly brewed coffee and tea will be served in the main foyer as well as chilled bottled water for your convenience.

PHOTOGRAPHY & VIDEOGRAPHY NOTICE

Photographs and video footage of you will be taken during the event. These photographs and/or video recordings may be used by the A*STAR Group for promotional, publicity and other related purposes. Please refer to our PDPA statement at <https://www.acrc.a-star.edu.sg/privacy.html> or contact our Data Protection Officer at dpo@acrc.a-star.edu.sg.

TRANSPORTATION

A daily shuttle service between Hotel Jen Tanglin and the conference venue at Biopolis has been arranged for all conference delegates staying at Hotel Jen Tanglin. Please refer to the schedule below:

	HOTEL - BIOPOLIS	BIOPOLIS - HOTEL
Tuesday, March 15	8:00am	6:30pm
Wenesday, March 16	8:00am	Bus to conference dinner
Thursday, March 17	8:00am	5:45pm and 6:45pm
Friday, March 18 *	subject to demand	subject to demand

MAIN PROGRAMME | TUESDAY, MARCH 15

START OF DAY 1	
08:00 - 09:00	Registration & Welcome Coffee
09:00 - 09:05	Opening Remarks Marek Michalewicz, A*STAR Computational Resource Centre, Singapore
09:05 - 09:20	Welcome Address Dr. Raj Thampuran, Managing Director, A*STAR, Singapore
09:20 - 09:40	National Supercomputing Centre Singapore MOU Ceremony National Supercomputing Centre Singapore
EXASCALE Chair: Marek Michalewicz	
09:40 - 10:25	Keynote Supercomputers and Superintelligence Horst Simon, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, USA
10:25 - 10:45	Break
APPLICATIONS Chair: Chee Yeow Meng	
10:45 - 11:15	The Potential for Exascale to Transform Healthcare Patricia Kovatch, Icahn School of Medicine, Mount Sinai Hospital, USA
11:15 - 11:45	Petascale Simulations of Microfluidics at Cell Resolution Diego Rossinelli, ETH Zurich, Switzerland
11:45 - 12:05	An Urgent Computing Framework for Ensembles of Forecasts on HPC Infrastructure <u>Siew Hoon Leong</u> & Dieter Kranz Müller, Leibniz Supercomputing Centre / Ludwig Maximilians University Munich, Germany
12:05 - 12:25	Transient Climate Impacts for Scenarios of Aerosol Emissions from Asia: A Story of Coal vs. Gas <u>Benjamin Grandey</u> & Haiwen Cheng, Singapore-MIT Alliance for Research and Technology, Singapore Chien Wang, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA
12:25 - 13:25	Lunch
APPLICATIONS & LANGUAGES Chair: Wong Weng Fai	
13:25 - 13:55	Why Now Is The Best Time To Adopt Julia Alan Edelman, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA

EXASCALE STORAGE & FILE SYSTEMS | Chair: Wong Weng Fai

13:55 - 14:25	<p>Exascale I/O : Burst Buffer and Beyond Jean-Thomas Acquaviva, DataDirect Networks, France</p>
14:25 - 14:45	<p>Zero Copy Architecture and File Systems Future Robert Mollard , SGI, Australia</p>
14:45 - 15:05	<p>Providing Low-overhead Data Consistency in Emerging Non-volatile Memory Jun Yang, Data Storage Institute, A*STAR, Singapore</p>
15:05 - 15:25	<p>Exascale Storage Systems the Sirius Way <u>Scott Klasky</u>, Hasan Abbasi, Qing Gary Liu, Jong Choi, Norbert Podhorszki & Feiyi Wang, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, USA Matthew Wolf, Georgia Institute of Technology, USA Matthew Curry & Jay Lofstead, Sandia National Laboratory, USA Mark Ainsworth, Brown University, USA Tahsin Kurc, Stony Brook University, USA Carlos Maltzahn, University of California, Santa Cruz, USA Manish Parashar, Rutgers University, USA C.S. Chang, Stephane Ethier & Michael Churchill, Princeton Plasma Physics Laboratory, USA</p>
15:25 - 15:45	<p>Break</p>
<p>VISUALISATION & APPLICATIONS Chair: Marian Vajtersic</p>	
15:45 - 16:05	<p>Visualization Plugins using VTKm for In-Transit Visualization with ADIOS Dave Pugmire, Jeremy Meredith, <u>Scott Klasky</u>, Jong Choi & Norbert Podhorszki, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, USA James Kress & Hank Childs, University of Oregon, USA</p>
16:05 - 16:25	<p>MateriApps – A Portal to Materials Science Simulation <u>Synghe Todo</u>, Ryo Igarashi, Shunsuke Kasamatsu, Takeko Kato, Naomi Kawashima, Yusuke Konishi, Hikaru Kouta, Kazuyoshi Yoshimi, University of Tokyo, Japan Tsutomu Kawatsu, Yokohama City University, Japan Haruhiko Matsuo & Kanako Yoshizawa, Research Organization for Information Science and Technology, Japan Masashi Noda, Institute for Molecular Science, Japan Shoichi Masaki & Shigehiro Tsuchida, Ageha, Inc., Japan Yayoi Terada, Tohoku University, Japan</p>

MAIN PROGRAMME | TUESDAY, MARCH 15

16:25 - 16:40	Super-scalable CFD Solver HiFUN on IISc Petascale Computing Platform N. Balakrishnan, Indian Institute of Science, India
16:40 - 16:55	Large Eddy Simulation of Gas Fluidized Beds <u>Jingrong Liang</u> & Eldin Wee Chuan Lim, National University of Singapore, Singapore
16:55 - 17:10	Computational Fluid Dynamics Study of Heat Transfer in Gas Fluidized Beds through Immersed Tubes <u>Zhongyuan Hau</u> & Eldin Wee Chuan Lim, National University of Singapore, Singapore
COUNTRY REPORTS Chair: David Kahaner	
17:10 - 17:25	Update on Indian National Supercomputing Mission Rajat Moona, Centre for Development of Advanced Computing, India
17:25 - 17:40	Japanese HPCI, High Performance Computer Infrastructure, Past, Present and Future, for Open Science and Open Innovation Motoi Okuda, Research Organisation for Information Science & Technology, Japan
17:40 - 17:55	40 Years of Supercomputers in China Meng Guo, National Supercomputer Center in Jinan, China
17:55 - 18:10	National Supercomputing Centre: the future of HPC in Singapore Jon Lau, National Supercomputing Centre, Singapore
END OF DAY 1	

START OF DAY 2

08:00 - 09:00	Registration & Welcome Coffee
BRAIN, A.I. & SUPERCOMPUTING Chair: Horst Simon	
09:00 - 10:00	Keynote Could A Brain Ever Have A Mind? Baroness Susan Greenfield, Oxford University, United Kingdom
10:00 - 10:30	From Supercomputing to Superintelligence Roman Yampolskiy, University of Louisville, USA
10:30 - 10:50	Break
EXASCALE & LANGUAGES Chair: Marek Niezgódka	
10:50 - 11:35	Keynote Sequoia to Sierra: The LLNL Strategy Bronis R. de Supinski, Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, USA
11:35 - 12:05	Exascale Programming Models: Where Are We Now? Barbara Chapman, Stony Brook University, USA
12:05 - 12:35	In the Zone: HPC with Extempore Andrew Sorenson, The Australian National University, Australia
12:35 - 13:35	Lunch
LANGUAGES Chair: Patricia Kovatch	
13:35 - 13:55	PCJ – A Java Library for Scalable Heterogenous Parallel Computing Marek Nowicki, Łukasz Górski & Magdalena Ryczkowska, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland <u>Piotr Bala</u> , Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling, Poland
13:55 - 14:35	Panel Discussion The Brain in Silicon? John Gustafson (Moderator), Bronis de Supinski, Roman Yampolskiy, Andrew Sorenson & Horst Simon
INTERCONNECTS & TOPOLOGIES Chair: Bronis de Supinski	
14:35 - 14:55	A Dynamic Congestion Management System for InfiniBand Networks Fabrice Mizero & <u>Malathi Veeraraghavan</u> , University of Virginia, USA Qian Liu & Robert D. Russell, University of New Hampshire, USA John M. Dennis, National Center for Atmospheric Research, USA

MAIN PROGRAMME | WEDNESDAY, MARCH 16

14:55 - 15:15	Strategies for Topology Aware Job Mapping and Scheduling in Multidimensional Torus-based Petascale Systems <u>Jarek Nabrzyski</u> & Kangkang Li, University of Notre Dame, USA Maciej Malawski, AGH University of Science & Technology, Poland
SYSTEM MONITORING Chair: Bronis de Supinski	
15:15 - 15:35	Making Large-Scale Systems Observable — Another Inescapable Step Towards Exascale <u>Dmitry Nikitenko</u> , Sergey Zhumatiy & Pavel Shvets, Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia
15:35 - 15:55	Break
INFINICORTEX Chair: Robert Harrison	
15:55 - 16:15	Around The Globe Towards Exascale: InfiniCortex – Past and Present Gabriel Noaje, A*STAR Computational Resource Centre, Singapore
16:15 - 16:45	How Can We Bridge Supercomputing, Next Generation Networks, Big Data and Applications? Krzysztof Kurowski, Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center, Poland
16:45 - 17:05	The Role of Standards in Supercomputing David Southwell, Obsidian Strategics, Canada
17:05 - 17:35	InfiniCloud 2.0: Distributing High Performance Computing Across Continents <u>Jakub Chrzesczyk</u> , Andrew Howard, The Australian National University, Australia Andrzej Chrzesczyk, Jan Kochanowski University, Poland
18:00 - 21:30	Conference Dinner at 1-Altitude
END OF DAY 2	

START OF DAY 3	
08:00 - 09:00	Registration & Welcome Coffee
NEW PROCESSOR ARCHITECTURES Chair: Srinivas Aluru	
09:00 - 09:45	A Radical Approach to Computation with Real Numbers John Gustafson, A*STAR Computational Resource Centre, Singapore
09:45 - 10:15	A New Processor Architecture for Exascale and Beyond Thomas Sohmers, REX Computing, USA
10:15 - 10:35	Break
NEW PROCESSOR ARCHITECTURES Chair: John Gustafson	
10:35 - 11:05	The Last Computing Frontier: Quantum Computing Vern Brownell, D-Wave Systems Inc., Canada
11:05 - 11:35	Tables, Graphs, and Problems John Feo, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory & University of Washington, USA
11:35 - 12:05	TrueNorth, A Low-Power Bio-inspired Neurosynaptic Architecture for Sensory Processing Garrick Orchard, National University of Singapore, Singapore
12:05 - 13:05	Lunch
AUTOMATA PROCESSOR Chair: Barbara Chapman	
13:05 - 13:50	Keynote Automata Processing: A New Paradigm for Computing Srinivas Aluru, Georgia Institute of Technology, USA
13:50 - 14:15	Pushing the Frontiers of Supercomputing with Automata Computing Mircea Stan, University of Virginia, USA
14:15 - 14:30	VASim: An Open Virtual Automata Simulator for Automata Processing Research Jack Wadden and Kevin Skadron, University of Virginia, USA
14:30 - 14:45	Parallel Interval Stabbing on the Automata Processor Indranil Roy & Matt Grimm, Micron Technology, Inc., USA Ankit Srivastava & Srinivas Aluru, Georgia Institute of Technology, USA

MAIN PROGRAMME | THURSDAY, MARCH 17

14:45 - 15:00	<p>Accelerating Weeder: A DNA Motif Search Tool using the Micron Automata Processor</p> <p>Qiong Wang, National University of Defense Technology, China Mohamed El-Hadedy, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, USA Ke Wang & Kevin Skadron, University of Virginia, USA Presenter: <u>Jack Wadden</u>, University of Virginia, USA</p>
15:00 - 15:20	Break
MANY-CORE Chair: He Bing Sheng	
15:20 - 15:50	<p>What Have We Learned About Heterogeneous Supercomputing?</p> <p>Wen-mei Hwu, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, USA</p>
15:50 - 16:20	<p>Application Readiness for the Pre-Exascale HPC Phase</p> <p>Stan Posey, NVIDIA Corporation, USA</p>
16:20 - 16:50	<p>Many-Core Approaches to Combinatorial Problems</p> <p><u>Michael Krajecki</u>, Julien Loiseau, Christophe Jaillet, Francois Alin & Arnaud Renard, University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne, CReSTIC, France</p>
16:50 - 17:10	<p>Elastic Stencil Code for Cloud-based GPU Spot Instances</p> <p><u>Jun Zhou</u>, Yan Zhang & Weng-Fai Wong, National University of Singapore, Singapore</p>
17:10 - 17:25	Break
AUTOMATA PROCESSOR Chair: Mircea Stan	
17:25 - 18:25	<p>Panel Discussion Special Session to Engage Community Input for an Automata Computing Community Infrastructure</p> <p>Mircea Stan (Moderator), Jack Wadden & Audience</p>
18:25 - 18:30	<p>Closing Remarks</p> <p>Marek Michalewicz, A*STAR Computational Resource Centre</p>
END OF DAY 3	

Please proceed to Level 4 of the Matrix Building at Biopolis on 20 March from 8:00am to check in for your workshop and to find out your workshop room. All meal breaks will be provided. **Pre-registration is required to guarantee your place in the workshops.**

W1: AUTOMATA PROCESSOR CONCEPTS AND APPLICATIONS

Time: 9:00am - 5:00pm

Breaks: Morning & afternoon tea breaks & lunch

Presenter: Matt Grimm, Automata Processor Applications Engineer, Micron Technology
 Indranil Roy, Automata Processor Software Development Architect, Micron Technology
 Terry Leslie, Director of Automata Processor Business Development, Micron Technology
 Jack Wadden & Mircea Stan, University of Virginia

Overview: This will be a full day workshop, starting in the morning with a brief discussion of concepts and foundational principles. This will incorporate live demonstrations of automata running on hardware. The foundational section will end with a demonstration of Protomata, a protein motif search application. The foundational discussion will be followed by a theoretical discussion of automata processing and mapping various problems into the AP paradigm. Specific applications and research projects will be discussed where the automata processor shows promise. There will also be a discussion of the AP cluster installation at the Center for Automata Processing at the University of Virginia.

W2: OPENPOWER WORKSHOP

Time: 9:00am - 5:00pm

Breaks: Morning & afternoon tea breaks & lunch

Presenter: Norishige (Noly) Morimoto, Vice-President & Chief Technology Officer, IBM Asia Pacific
 Ganesan Narayanasamy, OpenPOWER leader in Education and Research, IBM India
 H. Peter Hofstee, Research Member, IBM Austin Research Laboratory

Overview: OpenPOWER Workshop to provide latest updates on various Industry based applications.

W3: GPU PROGRAMMING HANDS-ON: GETTING STARTED WITH GPUS FOR HPC & DEEP LEARNING

Time: 9:00am - 5:00pm

Breaks: Morning & afternoon tea breaks & lunch

Presenter: Pradeep Kumar Gupta, Lead HPC & Deep Learning Solutions Architect, NVIDIA, APJ
Gabriel Noaje, Senior Computational Scientist, A*STAR Computational Resource Centre

Overview: **Learn how to program GPUs.** With millions of GPU compute enabled GPUs sold to date, software developers, scientists and researchers are finding broad-ranging uses for GPU computing.

Get hands-on practice with OpenACC. OpenACC allows programmers to use simple compiler directives to identify which areas of code to accelerate, without requiring modification to the underlying code itself.

In this interactive class we will also introduce the rapidly developing technology of **Deep Learning accelerated by GPUs.** Recent advances in Deep Learning have led to a step change in performance in a number of machine perception tasks including visual perception, speech recognition and natural language understanding after decades of slow progress in these areas. We will tour the most popular software frameworks for Deep Learning with goal of helping you decide which framework best suits your application needs as a researcher or developer.

Important Note:

Participants are required to bring their own laptops for this workshop.

W4: GPU PROGRESS AND DEVELOPMENTS FOR HPC APPLICATIONS

Time: 9:00am – 1:00pm

Breaks: Morning tea break and lunch

Presenter: Stan Posey, HPC Program Manager, NVIDIA USA

Overview: Current trends in high performance computing have advanced towards the use of graphics processing units (GPUs) to achieve accelerator speed-ups for numerical operations common among HPC applications, across a range of computational scientific and engineering domains.

In recent years, this trend has led to GPUs becoming mainstream processors for acceleration of industry-leading commercial CAE software from ISVs such as ANSYS, SIMULIA, and other vendors, and for widely used community developed software including OpenFOAM, WRF, COSMO, and several others.

This session will examine:

- Performance characteristics and requirements of HPC algorithms common to application software in the domains of computational mechanics and atmospheric modelling.
- Current state of GPU parallel solvers in production-use from commercial CAE vendors and considerations for optimal applied-use based on modeling and simulation objectives.
- Developments of GPU parallel atmospheric models and a review of the programming strategies deployed including the use of GPU-based libraries developed by NVIDIA and OpenACC – a directives-based programming model that preserves software portability.
- Select case studies will be reviewed that include deployment of GPUs for practice-level HPC and the application benefits they provide – in some cases transforming current modeling and simulation procedures.
- Review and discussion on NVIDIA directions of GPU hardware, application software development environment, and available programming models.

W5: EASILY DEPLOY DOCKER AND OPENSTACK WITH BRIGHT CLUSTER MANAGER AND BRIGHT OPENSTACK

Time: 9:00am - 5:00pm

Breaks: Morning & afternoon tea breaks & lunch

Presenter: Robert Stober, Director of Systems Solution Architects, Bright Computing

Overview: Containerisation and private clouds are gaining popularity in HPC environments. Through this workshop, participants will have the opportunity to learn first hand how to deploy, manage and monitor Docker containers using Bright Cluster Manager. In addition, participants will have hands on experience to deploy an Openstack private cloud "from scratch" using Bright Openstack.

Important notes:

- (a) This workshop is limited to 20 participants only.
- (b) Participants are required to bring their own laptop.
- (c) Prior to the workshop participants should install the Bright Cluster Manager front end client CMGUI for Bright Cluster Manager 7.2. Please refer to SCF2016 website for detailed instructions.

W6: PERFORMANCE TUNING ON INTEL MULTI AND MANY-CORE ARCHITECTURES

Time: 9:00am - 5:00pm

Breaks: Morning & afternoon tea breaks & lunch

Presenter: Mukesh Gangadhar, Senior Application Engineer, Intel

Overview: Hardware technologies in High Performance Computing are continuously undergoing major changes and rapidly increasing performance capabilities, but the software and the underlying code legacy is often left unchanged or even neglected. This leads to performance gaps and underutilized hardware assets.

In this workshop, gain insights into cutting-edge programming techniques and tools required to achieve the highest performance on Intel® Architecture using C/C++ or Fortran. Also, learn how to write code in order to maximize software performance on current and future Intel® Xeon and Xeon Phi processors (including Broadwell and Knights Landing).

Important Note:

Participants are required to bring their own laptops for this workshop.

W7: BREAKTHROUGH ENGINEERING USING HPC ON CLOUD

Time: 9:00am – 1:00pm

Breaks: Morning tea break and lunch

Presenter: Rajesh Chhabra, Vice President APAC – Enterprise Computing, Altair
Srirangam Srirangarajan, Managing Director – Altair Engineering Sdn Bhd.

Overview: Engineering is one of the most dynamic sector today. Rapidly changing demands – both in manpower and computing resources – make it also one of the most suitable for leveraging the Cloud. The need to collaborate across the globe with multi-disciplinary experts leveraging the best of the breed engineering applications is an absolute necessity.

These computation intensive engineering applications inturn depend on High Performance Computing (HPC) for quicker turnaround times. Faster turnarounds lead to faster collaboration which in turn would mean faster decision making.

Cloud computing’s unique ability to allow multiple collaborators to work on the same data models improves technical efficiency, data security and reduces potential errors due to miscommunication which in-turn reduces costs and improves overall efficiency.

This workshop is designed for Engineering R&D Heads, Engineering Leads, Product Design specialists and HPC infrastructure providers (technical + management). The workshop will showcase the Cloud solutions for organisations wanting to provide any software as a service and key engineering applications from Altair to enable breakthrough engineering for the modern era using HPC on Cloud.

W8: SPEEDING UP CFD SIMULATIONS FOR VARIOUS INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

Time: 9:00am - 5:00pm

Breaks: Morning & afternoon tea breaks & lunch

Presenter: Dr. Vincent Chai, Technical Sales Consultant, CAD-IT Consultants

Overview: In this workshop, participants will be able to experience the power and scalability of ANSYS computational fluid dynamics (CFD) solutions when paired with ANSYS HPC tools for various industry problems. In the recent release, ANSYS CFD with HPC was shown to scale from 768 cores to over 129,000 cores at 90% efficiency when solving complex fluid dynamic problems.

This workshop will go through different case studies with various applications for different industrial applications such as data centre cooling, multiphase analysis, turbomachinery studies and more.

W9: OPTIMIZING WITH HPC FOR ADVANCED MECHANICAL SIMULATION

Time: 9:00am – 1:00pm

Breaks: Morning tea break and lunch

Presenter: Hari Hara, Application Engineer, CAD-IT Consultants

Overview: In this workshop, participants will be able to experience the power of ANSYS HPC, parametric analysis and optimisation tools for mechanical design and simulation.

With ANSYS finite element analysis (FEA) tools, you can simulate real world behaviour of components and sub-systems. The ability to customize, automate and parameterize your simulations to analyse multiple design scenarios, allows you to test different design variations quickly and accurately. High-performance computing (HPC) adds tremendous value to engineering simulation by enabling the creation of large, high-fidelity models that yield accurate and detailed insight into the performance of a proposed design, predicting the actual performance of the product under real-world conditions.

W10: OVERCOMING ELECTROMAGNETICS CHALLENGES IN LARGE & COMPLEX SYSTEMS WITH HPC

Time: 2:00pm – 6:00pm

Breaks: Afternoon tea break

Presenter: Dr. Boyu Zheng, Technical Manager, CAD-IT Consultants

Overview: Modern electronics industry requires innovative approaches to design higher-speed, higher-throughput, better power efficiency and smaller form-factor electronics systems. As we are entering the era of Internet of Things (IoT), wireless communication and networking becomes equally important with the focus on wireless connectivity, antenna design, and electromagnetic interference and compatibility (EMI/EMC) issues. These systems are usually large and complex, therefore a lot of challenges are encountered during the stages of design and optimization.

ANSYS high-fidelity electromagnetic simulation software is ideal for identifying electromagnetic issues early in the design cycle. For example, the software enables engineers to do design space exploration to quickly identify the ideal solution for antenna design and placement. With HPC and ANSYS electromagnetics solution, engineers can effectively increase system performance and product reliability while reducing field failures.

In this workshop, participants will have the opportunity to understand the workflow of applying ANSYS electromagnetics solution to tackle real-world challenges in large and complex systems. There will also be hands-on sessions for participants to test out ANSYS and feel the solving capability with HPC.

W11: HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPUTING WITH JULIA

Time: 9:00am – 5:00pm

Breaks: Afternoon tea break

Presenter: Viral Shah, Co-inventor of Julia, Co-founder of Julia Computing

Overview: Julia is a high-level, high-performance, open source programming language for technical computing. It provides a sophisticated compiler, distributed parallel execution, numerical accuracy, and an extensive mathematical function library. Julia's Base library, largely written in Julia itself, also integrates mature, best-of-breed open source C and Fortran libraries for linear algebra, random number generation, signal processing, and string processing. In addition, the Julia developer community is contributing a number of external packages through Julia's built-in package manager at a rapid pace. IJulia, a collaboration between the Jupyter and Julia communities, provides a powerful browser-based graphical notebook interface to Julia.

This workshop will start with a basic introduction to Julia. It will then cover topics related to key scientific libraries (array manipulation, linear algebra, sparse matrices, FFTs, etc.). The participants will also learn how to write high performance Julia code, and what makes Julia so fast. Towards the end, we will discuss parallelism, multi-threading, and Julia on GPUs. In the second half, participants may translate their existing programs to Julia or work on an exercise to practise their julia skills.

See: <http://www.julialang.org/>

Important Note:

Participants are required to bring their own laptops for this workshop.

Join us for an all-day exclusive tour on **Monday, March 14, 2016** of research labs from the institutes below. This tour is reserved only for full-paying registrants of Supercomputing Frontiers 2016 and its speakers. Space is limited and pre-booking is essential.

8:45am	Meet at main entrance of Fusionopolis
9:00am	Departure from Fusionopolis
9:30am - 10:30am	Singapore Synchrotron Light Source (SSLS)
10:30am - 11:00am	Drive
11:00am - 12:00pm	Data Centres Tour: A*STAR Computational Resource Centre (A*CRC) National Supercomputing Centre Singapore (NSCC)
12:00pm - 1:00pm	Buffet Lunch at A*CRC
1:00pm - 1:15pm	Walk to Connexis North Tower
1:15pm - 2:00pm	Advanced Digital Sciences Centre (ADSC)
2:00pm - 2:45pm	Drive
2:45pm - 3:30pm	Earth Observatory of Singapore (EOS)
3:30pm - 4:15pm	Drive
4:15pm - 5:00pm	Future Cities Lab
5:00pm - 5:30pm	End of Tour

CONFERENCE DINNER - MARCH 16

The conference dinner will be on Wednesday, March 16, 2016 at Altimate in 1-Altitude, a world-class multi-concept lifestyle destination located 282 metres above sea level, boasting a truly spectacular unobstructed 360-degree view of Singapore.

Address: 1 Raffles Place, Central Business District (Raffles Place MRT, Exit B)

Dress code is smart casual.

Transport will be provided from the conference venue to 1-Altitude located in Singapore's central business district.

RSVPS are essential to guarantee your seat at the dinner.

Please note the following instructions:

- Buses will depart The Matrix at 6:00pm for 1-Altitude.
- Pre-dinner sunset drinks will be served from 6:30pm which will be followed by dinner at 7:00pm.
- A return bus to Hotel Jen Tanglin will depart at 9:45pm.
- All delegates must wear their name badge at all times.
- All delegates whose name badge has a cutlery icon will have access to the dinner.
- Organiser has the right to refuse entries for those who do not have their name badges or who have not registered for the dinner.

SRINIVAS ALURU

Srinivas Aluru is a professor in the School of Computational Science and Engineering within the College of Computing at Georgia Institute of Technology. Earlier, he held faculty positions at Iowa State University, Indian Institute of Technology, New Mexico State University, and Syracuse University. He conducts research in high performance computing, bioinformatics and systems biology, combinatorial scientific computing, and applied algorithms. He pioneered the development of parallel methods in computational biology, and contributed to the assembly and analysis of complex plant genomes. Aluru is a recipient of the NSF career award, IBM faculty award, Swarnajayanti Fellowship from the Government of India, and the mid-career and outstanding research achievement awards from Iowa State University. He is a Fellow of the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) and the Institute for Electrical and Electronic Engineers (IEEE).

BARONESS SUSAN GREENFIELD

Susan Greenfield is a research scientist, author and broadcaster based in Oxford. She has held research fellowships in the Department of Physiology Oxford, the College de France Paris, and NYU Medical Center New York. She has since been awarded 32 Honorary Degrees from British and foreign universities. In 2000 she was elected to an Honorary Fellowship of the Royal College of Physicians. Further international recognition of her work has included the 'Golden Plate Award' (2003) from the Academy of Achievement, Washington, the L'Ordre National de la Légion

d'Honneur (2003), from the French Government, and the 2010 Australian Medical Research Society Medal. She has recently held a Visiting Professorship at the Medical School, University of Melbourne, Australia for the month of November 2014 and 2015. She currently holds a Senior Research Fellowship at Oxford University, Lincoln College and is founder and CEO of a biotech company (www.neuro-bio.com) that is developing a novel anti-Alzheimer drug based on her research exploring novel brain mechanisms linked to neurodegeneration.

HORST SIMON

Horst Simon is an internationally recognized expert in the development of parallel computational methods for the solution of scientific problems of scale. His research interests are in the development of sparse matrix algorithms, algorithms for large-scale eigenvalue problems, and domain decomposition algorithms. His recursive spectral bisection algorithm is a breakthrough in parallel algorithms. Honored twice with the prestigious Gordon Bell Prize, most recently in 2009 for the development of innovative techniques that produce new levels of performance on a real application (in collaboration with IBM researchers) and in 1988 in recognition of superior effort in parallel

processing research (with others from Cray and Boeing). Horst Simon is Deputy Laboratory Director and Chief Research Officer (CRO) of Berkeley Labs. The Deputy Director is responsible for the overall integration of the scientific goals and objectives, consistent with the Laboratory's mission. Simon has been with Berkeley Labs since 1996, having served previously as Associate Laboratory Director for Computing Sciences, and Director of NERSC. His career includes positions at Stony Brook University, Boeing, NASA, and SGI. He received his Ph.D. in Mathematics from UC Berkeley, and a Diploma (M.A.) from TU Berlin, Germany. Simon is a SIAM Fellow and member of SIAM, ACM, and IEEE Computer Society.

BRONIS R. DE SUPINSKI

Bronis R. de Supinski is the Chief Technology Officer (CTO) for Livermore Computing (LC) at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL). In this role, he is responsible for formulating LLNL's large-scale computing strategy and overseeing its implementation. His position requires frequent interaction with high performance computing (HPC) leaders and he oversees several collaborations with the HPC industry as well as academia. Prior to becoming CTO for LC, Bronis led several research projects in LLNL's Center for Applied Scientific Computing. Most recently, he led the Exascale Computing Technologies (ExaCT) project and co-led the Advanced Scientific Computing (ASC) program's Application Development Environment and Performance Team (ADEPT). Throughout his career, Bronis has won several awards, including the prestigious Gordon Bell Prize in 2005 and 2006, as well as an R&D 100 for his leadership of a team that developed a novel scalable debugging tool. He is a member of the ACM and the IEEE Computer Society.

Jean-Thomas ACQUAVIVA, DataDirect Networks, France

N. BALAKRISHNAN, Indian Institute of Science, India

Vern BROWNELL, D-Wave Systems Inc., Canada

Barbara CHAPMAN, Stony Brook University, USA

Alan EDELMAN, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA

John FEO, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory and University of Washington, USA

GUO Meng, National Supercomputer Center in Jinan, China

John GUSTAFSON, A*STAR Computational Resource Centre, Singapore

Wen-mei HWU, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, USA

Patricia KOVATCH, Icahn School of Medicine, Mount Sinai Hospital, USA

Michael KRAJECKI, University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne, France

Krzysztof KUROWSKI, Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center, Poland

Jon LAU, National Supercomputing Centre, Singapore

Rob MOLLARD, Silico Graphics, AUSTRALIA

Rajat MOONA, Centre for Development of Advanced Computing, India

Motoi OKUDA, Research Organisation for Information Science & Technology, Japan

Garrick ORCHARD, National University of Singapore, Singapore

Stan POSEY, NVIDIA, USA

Diego ROSSINELLI, ETH Zurich, Switzerland

Thomas SOHMERS, REX Computing, USA

Andrew SORENSON, The Australian National University, Australia

David SOUTHWELL, Obsidian Strategics Inc., Canada

Mircea STAN, University of Virginia, USA

Roman YAMPOLSKIY, University of Louisville, USA

JUN YANG, Data Storage Institute, A*STAR, Singapore

Supercomputers and Superintelligence

Horst Simon, Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, USA

In recent years the idea of emerging superintelligence has been discussed widely by popular media, and many experts voiced grave warnings about its possible consequences. This talk will use an analysis of progress in supercomputer performance to examine the gap between current technology and reaching the capabilities of the human brain. In spite of good progress in high performance computing (HPC) and techniques such as machine learning, this gap is still very large. I will then explore two related topics through a discussion of recent examples: what can we learn from the brain and apply to HPC, e.g., through recent efforts in neuromorphic computing? And how much progress have we made in modeling brain function? The talk will be concluded with my perspective on the true dangers of superintelligence, and on our ability to ever build self-aware or sentient computers.

The Potential for Exascale to Transform Healthcare

Patricia Kovatch, Icahn School of Medicine, Mount Sinai Hospital, USA

High performance computing has already been enlisted in the quest to better understand, diagnose and treat human disease. Through the expert guidance of computational scientists and advanced computing and data analytic infrastructures, advances have been made in such areas as drug discovery and genomic sequencing. However, enormous scientific challenges lie ahead to realize the promise of personalized medicine. To achieve personalized medicine's full potential, commensurate advances to reach exascale also need to be made. This paper will outline the specific scientific challenges and impacts for three areas of medicine: personalized cardiac therapy, precision medicine and real-time accurate imaging diagnosis. Then it will discuss the limitations of existing HPC along with the expected computational and data parameters and new capabilities needed for each of these areas in 2025.

Petascale Simulations of Microfluidics at Cell Resolution

Diego Rossinelli, ETH Zurich, Switzerland

We discuss the features of uDeviceX, the petascale in-silico lab-on-a-chip. Microfluidic devices are essential for the detection of circulating tumor cells as prognostic markers of metastatic cancer. The unprecedented compute power offered by CUDA-enabled supercomputers allows us to contribute both on fundamental understanding and technological advancements in this field. The first production simulations have been deployed on Piz Daint and Titan after just 20 man-months of software development, from scratch, by embracing the Extreme Programming (XP) principles.

An Urgent Computing Framework for Ensembles of Forecasts on HPC Infrastructure

Siew Hoon Loong & Dieter Kranz Müller, Leibniz Supercomputing Centre/Ludwig Maximilians University Munich, Germany

Disasters can cause great economic losses and casualties and pose a challenge to political leaders to take appropriate prevention and mitigation actions. Forecasts of disasters can help relevant authorities to make timely educated decisions to mitigate financial losses, manage affected areas and reduce casualties. Stochastic approach, which improves forecast accuracy by leveraging on ensembles of forecasts, is used. To enable multiple forecasts with varying execution time to complete within a deadline under short order requires the adoption of a magnitude of resources. High performance computing (HPC) infrastructures, which are made up of a wide array of computing resources, are the natural choice. The aim is to provide a global, resilient urgent computing framework for disaster response to save lives and minimise material losses by maximising both the speed and accuracy of forecasts.

Transient Climate Impacts for Scenarios of Aerosol Emissions from Asia: A Story of Coal vs. Gas

Benjamin Grandey & Haiwen Cheng, Singapore-MIT Alliance for Research and Technology, Singapore
Chien Wang, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA

Fuel usage is an important driver of anthropogenic emissions of aerosols, particles suspended in the atmosphere. In Asia, it is possible that aerosol emissions may increase if business continues as usual, with economic growth driving an increase in coal burning. But it is also possible that emissions may decrease rapidly due to the widespread adoption of cleaner technologies or a shift towards non-coal fuels, such as natural gas. In this study, the transient climate impacts of two aerosol emissions scenarios are investigated: an RCP4.5 (Representative Concentration Pathway 4.5) control, which projects a decrease in anthropogenic aerosol emissions; and a scenario with enhanced anthropogenic aerosol emissions from Asia. A coupled atmosphere-ocean configuration of CESM (Community Earth System Model), including CAM5 (Community Atmosphere Model version 5), is used. Three sets of initial conditions are used to produce a three-member ensemble for each scenario. Enhanced Asian aerosol emissions are found to exert a large cooling effect across the Northern Hemisphere, partially offsetting greenhouse gas induced warming. Aerosol-induced suppression of the East Asian and South Asian summer monsoon precipitation occurs. The enhanced Asian aerosol emissions also remotely impact precipitation in other parts of the world. Over Australia, austral summer monsoon precipitation is enhanced, an effect associated with a southward shift of the intertropical convergence zone, driven by the aerosol-induced cooling of the Northern Hemisphere. Over the Sahel, West African monsoon precipitation is suppressed, likely via a weakening of the West African Westerly Jet. These results indicate that fuel usage in Asia, through the consequent aerosol emissions and associated radiative effects, might significantly influence future climate both locally and globally.

Why Now Is The Best Time To Adopt Julia

Alan Edelman, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA

Technical computing is evolving. Users are increasingly aware of the absurdity of parallelizing slow serial languages in order to obtain parallel performance. Users also do not want to be bound to overpriced commercial software.

In this talk we will demonstrate Julia and explain why on the surface it is rather similar to languages that many users find productive, but deep down explain why Julia is very different on the inside. We explain why Julia can run so very fast, and yet be so easy to use.

Exascale I/O : Burst Buffer and Beyond

Jean-Thomas Acquaviva, DataDirect Networks, France

Burst buffers have attracted a lot of academic attention in the last few years, and recently they start to concretize as an industrial reality. While, undoubtedly they appear as a promising building block for the Exascale I/O, they remain focused on acceleration for write dominated workloads.

An implicit yet important part of their appeal is the ability to leverage the arrival of the non-volatile memory by evolutionary means. One of the key learnings from the recent developments led at DDN is the necessity to go for a more global approach, and to shake the existing software stack in a more drastic way. We believe that non-volatile memory should be used to accelerate I/O globally not only write accesses.

Zero Copy Architecture and File Systems Future

Robert Mollard, Silicon Graphics, Australia

Traditional, POSIX based file systems are reaching their limits today and will not scale to meet the demands of forthcoming Exascale environments. Interim solutions such as burst buffer layer are aimed at addressing these challenges in the short term but they will only alleviate temporarily the challenges faced with a large single parallel file system design.

A quantum shift in how researchers work with their data in HPC will be required to maintain a cohesive environment for high performance computing that is able to scale, whilst continuing to deliver performance and data protection to these legacy requirements requires a new way of thinking about data management.

During this presentation, we will explore new ways to meet these challenges by looking at a new approach that we refer to as the "Zero Copy Architecture" or ZCA. We will explore emerging hardware architecture and software elements that could take HPC data management to the next level.

Providing Low-overhead Data Consistency in Emerging Non-volatile Memory

*Jun Yang, Data Storage Institute, A*STAR, Singapore*

The non-volatile memory (NVM) which can provide DRAM-like performance and disk-like persistency has the potential to replace both DRAM and disk. Keeping data consistency in NVM is non-trivial because memory writes may be reordered by CPU. Although ordered memory writes for achieving data consistency can be implemented using the memory fence and the CPU cache line flush instructions, they introduce a significant overhead (more than 10X slower in performance). In this talk, we focus on how to reduce such overhead and use an important and common data structure, B+Tree, as an example of our solution. Our NV-Tree is a consistent, cache-optimized and workload-adaptive B+Tree variant with significantly reduced consistency cost (up to 96% reduction in CPU cache line flush).

Exascale Storage Systems the Sirius Way

Scott Klasky, Hasan Abbasi, Qing Gary Liu, Jong Choi, Norbert Podhorszki & Feiyi Wang, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, USA

Matthew Wolf, Georgia Institute of Technology, USA

Matthew Curry & Jay Lofstead, Sandia National Laboratory, USA

Mark Ainsworth, Brown University, USA

Tahsin Kurc, Stony Brook University, USA

Carlos Maltzahn, University of California, Santa Cruz, USA

Manish Parashar, Rutgers University, USA

C.S. Chang, Stephane Ethier & Michael Churchill, Princeton Plasma Physics Laboratory, USA

As the exascale computing age emerges, data related issues are becoming critical factors that determine how and where we do computing. Popular approaches used by traditional I/O solution and storage libraries become increasingly bottlenecked due to their assumptions about data movement, re-organization, and storage. While, new technologies, such as “burst buffers”, can help address some of the short-term performance issues, it is essential that we reexamine the underlying storage and I/O infrastructure to effectively support requirements and challenges at exascale and beyond. In this paper we present a new approach to the exascale Storage System and I/O (SSIO), which is based on allowing users to inject application knowledge into the system and leverage this knowledge to better manage, store, and access large data volumes so as to minimise the time to scientific insights. Central to our approach is the distinction between the data, metadata, and the knowledge contained therein, transferred from the user to the system by describing “utility” of data as it ages.

Visualization Plugins using VTKm for In-Transit Visualization with ADIOS

Dave Pugmire, Jeremy Meredith, Scott Klasky, Jong Choi & Norbert Podhorszki, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, USA

James Kress & Hank Childs, University of Oregon, USA

The scientific data that are being generated today, and in the near future, will quickly out-pace our ability to process and understand it. The data generated are growing in multiple ways, including the size of the data, the rate at which it arrives, and the varying types of data. Additionally, data are available from multiple sources, including for example, computational simulations and sensor data extracted from experiments. In such situations, workflows for the movement and management of data, as well as the analysis and visualization while the data are in transit, become even more critical, and increasingly challenging. At the same time, revolutionary changes are emerging the architectures of supercomputers. These changes included a tremendous increases in concurrency and the number of execution threads available on each node. These architectures are a challenge for currently running HPC codes, including visualization and analysis algorithms. In this paper we discuss some early work focused on the development of in-transit visualization techniques that are deployable on a supercomputing center.

MateriApps – A Portal to Materials Science Simulation

Synge Todo, Ryo Igarashi, Shunsuke Kasamatsu, Takeko Kato, Naoki Kawashima, Yusuke Konishi, Hikaru Kouta, Kazuyoshi Yoshimi, University of Tokyo, Japan

Tsutomu Kawatsu, Yokohama City University, Japan

Haruhiko Matsuo & Kanako Yoshizawa, Research Organization for Information Science and Technology, Japan

Masashi Noda, Institute for Molecular Science, Japan

Shoichi Masaki & Shigehiro Tsuchida, Ageha, Inc., Japan

Yayoi Terada, Tohoku University, Japan

We present the MateriApps project that aims at forming a portal to materials science simulation. The goal of MateriApps is nurturing a community in the field of computational materials science through the promotion of open-source application software. In the MateriApps web, more than 160 applications/tools/databases are introduced with detailed information, and users can browse and search applications easily based on methods, target materials, interesting phenomena, physical quantities, etc. In addition, in order to build up infrastructure for experts and non-experts to start materials science simulations quickly, we develop MateriApps Installer and develop MateriApps LIVE! package. In the poster presentation, the entire picture of the MateriApps project, the current status, and future issues will be discussed together with some demonstration of the MateriApps web and tutorials of materials science simulation using the MateriApps LIVE! package.

Super-scalable CFD Solver HiFUN on IISc Petascale Computing Platform

N. Balakrishnan, Indian Institute of Science, India

The HiFUN solver (High resolution Flow solver on Unstructured meshes) is a general purpose CFD solver for aerospace and automotive applications. The talk would establish the super scalability of the HiFUN solver on the Cray XC40 system available at SERC (Supercomputer Education and Research center), Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore. It would be demonstrated that even with sub-domain sizes as small as 3000 volumes, it is possible to obtain high parallel efficiencies on the Cray XC40 using the HiFUN solver. This feature allows the HiFUN solver to truly exploit the Peta scale computing platform. The algorithmic scalability (ability to recover serial performance on a parallel platform) of the HiFUN solver even when very large number of processor cores are employed, would be established. This enables building robust CFD processes on the Cray system, around the HiFUN solver. In the process, an attempt to compare the performance of few super computing platforms using the HiFUN would be made. The impressive turn around time the Cray XC40 offers in solving large scale CFD problems involving over 100 million volumes would be highlighted.

Large Eddy Simulation of Gas Fluidized Beds

Jingrong Liang & Eldin Wee Chuan Lim, National University of Singapore, Singapore

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) was applied for simulation of a three-dimensional fluidized bed to study the effectiveness of various turbulence models coupled with various multiphase models in replicating hydrodynamic profiles within the fluidized bed. For bubbling fluidization, the Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) based turbulence model, in particular the Shear Stress Transport (SST) $k-\omega$ model in conjunction with the Eulerian multiphase framework provided close agreement with experimental results reported by other researchers. For the turbulent fluidization regime, neither RANS nor the Large Eddy Simulation (LES)/Detached Eddy Simulation (DES) turbulence models were adequate in simulating the hydrodynamics within the fluidized bed. The realizable $k-\epsilon$ model coupled with the Eulerian multiphase model produced the best representation of core-annular flow characteristics. For all fluidization regimes considered, the LES/DES models were unable to replicate the hydrodynamics observed in experiments due to over-predictions of particle velocities or voidage. This might be attributed to inaccuracies associated with the multiphase model that was coupled with the turbulence models applied.

Computational Fluid Dynamics Study of Heat Transfer in Gas Fluidized Beds through Immersed Tubes

Zhongyuan Hau & Eldin Wee Chuan Lim, National University of Singapore, Singapore

An Eulerian-Eulerian approach was used to study the coupled effects of hydrodynamics and heat transfer in a mono-dispersed bubbling fluidized bed with an immersed tube. The main mode of heat transfer from the heated tube to the bulk phase was observed to be via conductive heat transfer through particle contact with the heated tube. Particle renewal facilitated heat transfer as heated particles on the surface of the heated tube were replaced with cooler particles which led to higher temperature gradient that drives heat transfer. The increase in particle size led to the

formation of larger bubbles, and consequently resulted in decrease in conductive heat transfer. The increase in tube temperature led to a corresponding increase in heat transfer coefficient values, despite a decrease in solids distribution around the heated tube. This suggested that temperature gradient was the primary driving force for heat transfer. The coupled effects on heat transfer was also demonstrated with the use of different drag laws that produced significantly different hydrodynamics and heat transfer efficiency.

DAY 1 | COUNTRY REPORTS

Update on Indian National Supercomputing Mission

Rajat Moona, Centre for Development of Advanced Computing, India

Abstract unavailable at the time of printing.

Japanese HPCI, High Performance Computer Infrastructure, Past, Present and Future, for Open Science and Open Innovation

Motoi Okuda, Research Organisation for Information Science & Technology, Japan

In 2006, based on the 3rd Science and Technology Basic plan, Japanese Government started the K computer project, which targeted to develop world top class supercomputing environment. In 2012, the innovative High Performance Computing Infrastructure (HPCI) was built by connecting flagship K computer and other eleven major supercomputers in Japan via SINET4/5, the high speed Japanese academic network backbone.

HPCI also provides several HPC user support features, such as a Single Sign On (SSO) based user interface, unified help desk, program tuning and visualization support. These features may accelerate and maximize the outcome of the projects. Users who want to use HPCI systems including K computer are requested to apply the Call for proposals for research projects. This call is open to the global academic HPC community.

After four years of HPCI operations, many projects achieved distinguished results. The outcome of these projects is open to the global HPC community through the HPCI web site, http://www.hpci-office.jp/pages/e_result.

In 2014, after a two years feasibility study, the FLAGSHIP 2020 Project which targets to develop the next generation flagship supercomputer in Japan (the Post K computer) and to start operation in 2020, was launched by the Japanese Government along with a wide range of applications that will address top priority social and scientific issues.

RIKEN was appointed as the organization for leading the project and Fujitsu was selected as basic-design and design & implementation phase contractor.

The Post K computer will consist of general-purpose many-cores processors. By adopting a co-design approach, the system will be designed to maximize the performance of targeted application area. Nine themes were selected as social and scientific priority issues and are expected to achieve world-leading outcomes by using post K computer.

The 5th Science and Technology Basic Plan of Japan is scheduled to start from April 2016. Through the collaboration with the global HPC community, HPCI and Post K computer are expected to contribute to Open science and Open innovation which addresses in the plan.

40 Years of Supercomputers in China

Meng Guo, National Supercomputer Center in Jinan, China

From the first modern supercomputer Yinhe-I with the performance of 100 MFLOPS in 1980s to the six successive world championships Tianhe-II with the peak performance of 54.9 PFLOPS in recent three years, China's supercomputer has experienced super development to meet the increasing needs of scientific and engineering computing in geological exploration, weather forecasting, climate research, universe evolution, aircraft design, drug design and many other areas. For about four decades, several serials of supercomputers such as Yinhe, Tianhe, Shenwei and Dawning etc., have been developed by universities, research institutes and companies under the financial support from Chinese government, meanwhile the applications of supercomputers also nurture Chinese economy, science, education as well as a lot of upstream and downstream industries, which will boost the development of new supercomputer. This report will review the history and development of supercomputers in China in the past about four decades. A technical comparison of their architectures including the processor, memory, network and storage as well as the status of the investors, producers, operators and consumers will be discussed. This report will also give a brief introduction of the national research project of high performance computing for the next five years, and analyze the impact of policies, new technologies and products on the next generation supercomputers.

National Supercomputing Centre: The Future of HPC in Singapore

Jon Lau, National Supercomputing Centre, Singapore

Abstract unavailable at the time of printing.

Could A Brain Ever Have A Mind?

Baroness Susan Greenfield, Oxford University, United Kingdom

If we think of a 'mind' as a subjective inner state, then there are two ways in which we might link 'minds' with computers. First, a silicon model: however the point of a model is to extract the salient feature from the extraneous components. For example, if modelling flight the salient feature would be to defy gravity, yet with no need for beaks and feathers. But with the 'mind' the appropriate salient feature to model, is far from obvious. Alternatively, we can argue that a mind will be an automatically emergent property of ever more complex systems, irrespective of the material from which they are constituted. Yet then we are overlooking all-important qualitative biological features: the trafficking of a huge variety of powerful and distinct compounds in the nervous system that work in different combinations, in different places, over different windows of time, with highly context-dependent and variable effects. In particular, we need to consider 'neuronal assemblies', i.e. transient coalitions of millions of brain cells of sub-second duration and extending over large areas of brain. We shall see how this collective output could correspond to one-off holistic brain states, specifically a moment of consciousness that could not readily be replicated in artificial systems.

From Supercomputing to Superintelligence

Roman Yampolskiy, University of Louisville, USA

Many scientists, futurologists and philosophers have predicted that humanity will achieve a technological breakthrough and create superintelligence within the next one hundred years. Significant progress in supercomputers is very likely to result in creation of superintelligent machines. It has been suggested that superintelligence will have a significant positive or negative impact on humanity. In this talk, I will discuss how supercomputer-based superintelligence will influence different domains of human pursuits.

Sequoia to Sierra: The LLNL Strategy

Bronis R. de Supinski, Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, USA

Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) has a long history of leadership in large-scale computing. Our current platform, Sequoia, is a 96 rack BlueGene/Q system that is currently number three on the Top 500 list. Our next platform, Sierra, will be a heterogeneous system delivered by a partnership between IBM, NVIDIA and Mellanox. While the platforms are diverse, they represent a carefully considered strategy. In this talk, we will compare and contrast these platforms and the applications that run on them, and provide a glimpse into LLNL's strategy beyond Sierra.

Exascale Programming Models: Where Are We Now?

Barbara Chapman, Stony Brook University, USA

Research and development efforts around the world are exploring hardware and software solutions that may help build exascale computers with unprecedented levels of application performance and acceptable power consumption.

No aspect of the race to design and develop exascale systems has been more hotly debated than the programming models that will be needed to create application codes capable of exploiting these exceptionally complex platforms. Many potential solutions have been proposed, from revolutionary paths via special purpose languages to evolutionary approaches. We discuss the status of programming models that may play a role in the exascale landscape, and the challenges that lie ahead.

In the Zone: HPC with Extempore

Andrew Sorenson, The Australian National University, Australia

Extempore is a new HPC research language with an unusual pedigree. Designed with a focus on live-coding “down-to-the-metal,” Extempore’s domain focus was originally interactive media arts - particularly real-time digital signal processing, and interactive computer graphics applications. It was soon realized however, that the same kinds of parallel heavy-numeric compute problems that arise in real-time interactive media applications, are also common to HPC applications.

Extempore is a new systems programming language, designed to mix the low-level expressiveness of C with the high-level expressiveness of Lisp. Extempore supports a static type system, with code inference. Parametric polymorphism, with total static code specialisation. Temporal-semantics for code scheduling and deadline handling. On-the-node compilation and code hot-swapping across distributed clusters. Zone-based resource management where zones can be optionally distributed.

In this talk, Andrew will give a brief hands-on demonstration of Extempore, with examples drawn from a number of application domains.

DAY 2 | LANGUAGES

PCJ – A Java Library for Scalable Heterogenous Parallel Computing

*Marek Nowicki, Łukasz Górski & Magdalena Ryczkowska, Nicolaus Copernicus University, Poland
Piotr Bala, Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling, Poland*

PCJ is a library for Java language that helps to perform parallel and distributed calculations. It is able to work on the multicore systems with the typical interconnect such as ethernet or InfiniBand providing users with the uniform view across nodes. The library is OpenSource (BSD license) and its source code is available at GitHub.

PCJ implements partitioned global address space model and was inspired by languages like Co-Array Fortran, Unified Parallel C and Titanium. We put emphasis on compliance with Java standards. In contrast to the listed languages, the PCJ does not extend nor modify language syntax. The programmer does not have to use additional libraries, which are not part of the standard Java distribution.

The PCJ library has been successfully used to parallelize a number of applications including typical HPC benchmarks receiving HPC Challenge Award at Supercomputing Conference (SC 2014).

The parallelization of selected applications show good performance and good scalability of Java implementation with the PCJ library. The resulting code is simple, usually contains fewer lines of code than other solutions. This is obtained thanks to the PGAS programming model and one-sided asynchronous communication implemented in the PCJ. Therefore, the parallelization is easier than in the other programming models. The communication and synchronization cost is comparable to other implementations such as MPI resulting in good performance and scalability.

DAY 2 | INTERCONNECTS & TOPOLOGIES

A Dynamic Congestion Management System for InfiniBand Networks

Fabrice Mizero & Malathi Veeraraghavan, University of Virginia, USA

Qian Liu & Robert D. Russell, University of New Hampshire, USA

John M. Dennis, National Center for Atmospheric Research, USA

Run times of scientific applications when executed on InfiniBand networks have high variability. A cause of this variability is network congestion. The InfiniBand congestion control mechanism is typically disabled because of the difficulty in selecting appropriate settings for its parameters. We propose a Dynamic Congestion Management System (DCMS) to address this problem. Lacking per-flow information, the DCMS leverages performance counters of switch ports to detect onset of congestion, and determines whether-or-not victim flows are present. The DCMS then takes actions to cause an aggressive reduction in the sending rates of congestion causing (contributor) flows if victim flows are present. On the other hand, in the absence of victim flows, the DCMS allows the contributor flows to maintain high sending rates and finish as quickly as possible. The solution is evaluated in an experimental testbed. Our results show that dynamic congestion management can enable a network to serve both contributor flows and victim flows effectively.

Strategies for Topology Aware Job Mapping and Scheduling in Multidimensional Torus-based Petascale Systems

Jarek Nabrzyski & Kangkang Li, University of Notre Dame, USA

Maciej Malawski, AGH University of Science & Technology, Poland

Communication networks in recent high performance computing machines are often built with multidimensional torus topologies. System's topology influences the way jobs should be scheduled and mapped onto the system. Contiguous allocation strategy is often used to improve the application performance and runtime consistency. In such an approach, each job is allocated a

convex prism, which reduces job-to-job interference and improves job performance. However, this contiguous allocation will result in a degradation of system utilization. A convex prism leads to internal fragmentation inside the job, and the contiguous allocation strategy has the side effect of external fragmentation. Pure non-contiguous allocation can improve the system utilization to a great extent. However, using this strategy causes job performance to go down due to communication interference, which results in increased latency. In this paper, we present several techniques to mitigate these various negative behaviours of such systems.

DAY 2 | SYSTEM MONITORING

Making Large-Scale Systems Observable — Another Inescapable Step Towards Exascale

Dmitry Nikitenko, Sergey Zhumatiy & Pavel Shvets, Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia

The effective mastering of extremely parallel HPC system is impossible without deep understanding of all internal processes and behaviour of the whole diversity of the components: computing processors and nodes, memory usage, interconnect, storage, whole software stack, cooling and so forth in detail. There are numerous visualization tools that provide information on certain components and system as a whole, but most of them have severe issues that limit appliance in real life, thus becoming unacceptable for the future system scales. Predefined monitoring systems and data sources, lack of dynamic on-the-fly reconfiguration, inflexible visualization and screening options are among most popular issues. The proposed approach to monitoring data processing resolves the majority of known problems providing a scalable and flexible solution based on any available monitoring systems and other data sources. The approach implementation is successfully used in every-day practice of the largest in Russia Supercomputer Center of Moscow State University.

DAY 2 | INFINICORTEX

Around The Globe Towards Exascale: InfiniCortex – Past and Present

*Gabriel Noaje, A*STAR Computational Resource Centre, Singapore*

The InfiniCortex is a tightly coupled system of distributed, concurrent HPC resources connected through a worldwide InfiniBand fabric circumnavigating the globe and bringing together number of supercomputing facilities spanned across four continents (Asia, Australia, Europe and North America). Over the last two years the project brought together 23 academic and commercial partners from around the world and showcased several world premieres such as:

- the largest ever spanning InfiniBand network – a ring-around-the-world with most of the segments at 100Gbps and few at 10-30Gbps;
- InfiniBand routing between eight subnets created using InfiniBand routers;
- InfiniCloud: high throughput HPC cloud provisioned as single, simultaneous instances across four continents;
- number of HPC applications and workflows running successfully over InfiniCortex infrastructure.

Using very long distance InfiniBand connections that establish a new architectural approach might fulfill the challenge of building the next generation of HPC systems to solve complex problems through the aggregation and parallelization of many globally distributed supercomputers into a single hive-mind of enormous scale.

In this presentation I will report the definitive history, from the conception in early 2014 to the current status, of the InfiniCortex project which was initiated and led by A*STAR Computational Resource Centre (A*CRC).

How Can We Bridge Supercomputing, Next Generation Networks, Big Data and Applications?

Krzysztof Kurowski, Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center, Poland

With the constant growth of scientific data to be analysed in nearly real-time, the in-situ interactive visualisation as a user-facing service is getting now the attention of many scientific communities. The basic idea is to perform remotely data analytics and advanced visualization during advanced computing simulations or large data processing operations. Consequently, users could quickly react or even steer advanced simulations at any stage and from any location in the world, for instance check whether algorithm parameters were set correctly or they have to be modified on demand due to instability. In fact, such a scenario and testbed have been setup experimentally for selected parallel applications. Moreover, the scenario has been successfully demonstrated at SC'15 and TNC15 conferences using supercomputing facilities in Singapore, Europe and the United States linked globally together via new optical networking technologies. However, achieving such a global computing environment where high-speed and reliable networks are synchronise in time with the access to large computing and data resources is not a trivial task. Therefore, in this talk many lessons learned and best practices will be shared together with the update of emerging and promising technologies in all these fields based on recent improvements to the PSNC e-infrastructure.

The Role of Standards in Supercomputing

David Southwell, Obsidian Strategics, Canada

There is an interesting tension between the need to deliver state of the art equipment delivering bleeding edge performance and the well understood benefits of deploying open standards based technologies. Illustrated by a brief history of the last few decades of supercomputing, this talk explores the phenomenon of oscillation between exotic and generic hardware and software, and how the user communities have been served by these trends. The Exascale campaign is currently driving innovation, reflecting a realisation that machines at this scale cannot feasibly be constructed by linear extension of existing architectures and that cost effective transistor scaling can no longer be relied upon. The InfiniCortex architecture is considered as a way to preserve the clear benefits of a standards based approach, even while silicon building blocks trend inevitably to highly integrated monolithic solutions in response to these pressures.

InfiniCloud 2.0: Distributing High Performance Computing Across Continents

*Jakub Chrzesczyk, Andrew Howard, The Australian National University, Australia
Andrzej Chrzesczyk, Jan Kochanowski University, Poland*

InfiniCloud is a distributed cloud platform specifically designed to support high performance computing. The hardware configuration of the system includes high performance Intel™ CPU, 128-256GB memory, SSD/NVMe storage as well as InfiniBand network.

The novel interconnect design of the system, using global range InfiniBand, now enhanced with an addition of routable, independent subnets, allows greater flexibility and deployment in a number of scenarios, from loosely coupled systems providing global IB connectivity between the instances for high performance data movement, to tightly coupled systems allowing distributing a single job across multiple physical locations on four different continents.

The first scenario was discussed in detail in earlier work presented at Supercomputing Frontiers 2015 [InfiniCloud: Leveraging the Global InfiniCortex Fabric and OpenStack Cloud for Borderless High Performance Computing of Genomic Data; K. Ban, J. Chrzesczyk, A. Howard, D. Li, T.W. Tan; Performance Assessment of InfiniBand HPC Cloud Instances on Intel Haswell and Intel Sandy Bridge Architectures; J. Low, J. Chrzesczyk, A. Howard, A. Chrzesczyk]. This paper focuses solely on the second mode of operation - building a system capable of distributing a computation between locations in Asia, Australia, Europe and the United States.

A Radical Approach to Computation with Real Numbers

*John Gustafson, A*STAR Computational Resource Centre, Singapore*

If we are willing to give up compatibility with IEEE 754 floats and design a number format with goals appropriate for 2016, we can achieve several goals simultaneously: Extremely high energy efficiency and information-per-bit, no penalty for decimal operations instead of binary, rigorous bounds on answers without the overly pessimistic bounds produced by interval methods, and unprecedented high speed up to some precision. This approach extends the ideas of unum arithmetic introduced two years ago by breaking completely from the IEEE float-type format, resulting in fixed bit size values, fixed execution time, no exception values or "gradual underflow" issues, no wasted bit patterns, and no redundant representations (like "negative zero"). Call them "tunums," for "terse universal numbers." As an example of the power of this format, a difficult 12-dimensional nonlinear robotic kinematics problem that has defied solvers to date is quickly solvable with absolute bounds. Also unlike interval methods, it becomes possible to operate on arbitrary disconnected subsets of the real number line with the same speed as operating on a simple bound. These new numerical entities are SORNs (Sets Of Real Numbers), which are radically different from symbolic data structures for sets in that they have fixed size and are operated on with simple bit operations. As a final note, the approach shows the possibility of creating application-specific numeric systems that do not require custom hardware to run quickly.

A New Processor Architecture for Exascale and Beyond

Thomas Sohmers, REX Computing, USA

While existing processor architectures applied for general purpose HPC workloads have begun to reach fundamental limits with the end of Moore's law approaching, the two main barriers to having an Exascale machine is energy efficiency and scalability. Recently, more emphasis has been put performance per watt and code that can scale to many millions of cores, but the current major processor vendors have resorted to incremental improvements on designs that are pushing 30 years old rather than designing for the challenges of today. REX Computing is developing the Neo processor architecture to address these problems, and through a fundamental rethinking of how memory is handled on a chip, is producing a new HPC focused processor going beyond the Exascale requirements for sustained performance, memory bandwidth, and energy efficiency. This talk will give an overview of the architecture and insight on key design decisions, as well as specifics on the first silicon that will be available in 2016 and software tools enabling a transition from existing architectures.

The Last Computing Frontier: Quantum Computing

Vern Brownell, D-Wave Systems Inc., Canada

Despite the incredible power of today's supercomputers, there are many computationally-intensive applications that can't be addressed by conventional systems. Quantum computers have left the laboratory and offer the potential to help solve some of the most complex technical, commercial, scientific, and national defence problems that organizations face. Vern Brownell, CEO of the world's first quantum computing company, will explain how quantum computers work, how they can complement HPC systems, and the impact they may have on reshaping the computing landscape.

Tables, Graphs, and Problems

John Feo, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory & University of Washington, USA

The availability of data is changing the way scientific and business communities operate. Economic competitiveness and national security depend increasingly on the insightful analysis of large data sets. The volume, variety, velocity, and veracity of data sets and the breadth of analytic processes pose unique computational challenges. Traditional table-based methods are being supplemented by graph methods that operate on sparse data capturing dynamic relationships among typed entities. Consequently, analytic platforms must support both in a natural way without preference. In this talk, I will summarize the hybrid nature of big data, the consequences of scale-free real world data sets, and essential runtime requirements for scalable performance. I will describe how we are addressing these challenges in GEMS 2.0, a second-generation database platform. The first generation database was pure graph (RDF triples, SPARQL queries, and constrained graph isomorphism), and we found it inadequate for many real-world problems. So, we redesigned the database to support both tables and property graphs, and have extended SQL to define graph views and queries. GEMS 2.0 sits atop a custom, fine-grain, multithreaded runtime system that scales on conventional server and HPC systems.

TrueNorth, A Low-Power Bio-inspired Neurosynaptic Architecture for Sensory Processing

Garrick Orchard, National University of Singapore, Singapore

Advances in multi-layer neural networks are giving machines the ability to perform sensory processing tasks at or near human-level accuracy for the first time. However, the power consumption of these systems is still orders of magnitude higher than that of their biological counterparts, and as the quantity of sensory data being recorded continues to grow exponentially, new approaches are required for sensory processing, both in terms of technology and strategy. Sensory data is inherently captured in real-time, and can take on a wide variety of forms, but regardless of the nature of the data, its value is maximized if it can be processed with minimal latency to allow for real-time reaction. This is precisely the regime in which biological brains excel, they can integrate and co-ordinate multiple sensory and motor modalities in real-time. As part of the DAPRA SyNAPSE program, IBM has developed "TrueNorth", a neurosynaptic architecture inspired by the impressive capabilities of biological brains and representing a radical departure

from traditional von Neumann architectures. At the heart of the TrueNorth ecosystem lies the TrueNorth chip, measuring 4.3cm^2 and capable of simulating 1 million neurons and 256 million synapses in real-time with a power consumption of only 100mW. TrueNorth chips can directly interface to each other, allowing them to easily scale to create even larger systems. Low power consumption is achieved through a combination of the process choice (28nm Samsung), the use of an asynchronous design methodology, and the co-location of memory and computational elements in individual cores (of which there are 4096 per chip) to ensure bits are never moved very far. In this talk, I will describe TrueNorth, how different elements of the chip relate to the biological systems from which they are inspired, and some of the results obtained thus far using TrueNorth systems in sensory processing tasks.

DAY 3 | AUTOMATA PROCESSOR

Automata Processing: A New Paradigm for Computing

Srinivas Aluru, Georgia Institute of Technology, USA

This talk will introduce the Micron Automata Processor (AP), a novel computing architecture that permits massively parallel execution of numerous non-deterministic finite automata. The processor inspires a new programming paradigm of solving problems using complex pattern matching engines executed over streaming data. The first part of this talk will focus on the processor characteristics, programming and execution environment, and design principles we discovered that are of value in developing applications on the AP. The second part will feature my group's research over the past four years to develop algorithms and applications using the AP, and broaden the applicability of this architecture beyond direct pattern matching applications. In particular, I will present techniques to solve several classical problems on unweighted graphs.

Pushing the Frontiers of Supercomputing with Automata Computing

Mircea Stan, University of Virginia, USA

The Automata Processor (AP) developed by Micron Technology is a fundamentally new hardware computing architecture capable of performing high-speed, comprehensive search and analysis of complex, unstructured data streams necessary for current and especially future Supercomputing tasks. A highly scalable fabric of interconnected processing elements, the AP delivers unprecedented, energy efficient parallelism while avoiding many of the complexities inherent in standard parallel programming. The Automata Processor is especially powerful because it implements natively in hardware the non-deterministic finite automata (NFA) paradigm from classic computer science theory - the non-determinism property allows many states to be active at once. This allows the AP to explore many potential candidate matches in parallel, thus making it capable of solving "fuzzy" matching problems, even those with combinatorial search spaces; in this regard, it bears some similarity to quantum computing. The AP also complements the extreme data parallelism typical of conventional supercomputer MIMD and SIMD solutions with the extreme instruction parallelism of an unconventional MISD architecture. The AP is particularly effective at leveraging the MISD property thanks to its large capacity. A single chip holds over 49,000 states, all of which are concurrently scanning and responding to the input stream; and Micron's initial boards hold 32 chips, thus providing over 1.5 million states, all operating concurrently.

VASim: An Open Virtual Automata Simulator for Automata Processing Research

Jack Wadden and Kevin Skadron, University of Virginia, USA

We present VASim, an open, virtual automata simulator for automata processing research. VASim is written in C++ using object-oriented design making it easy to understand and extend. VASim allows users to implement automata transformation and optimization passes, for increased performance. VASim is parametrically multi-threaded, and can automatically divide connected automata components, and sections of the input stream among parallel threads. We compare performance of VASim against two available automata processing tools, and show 10 to 1000 times speedups.

Parallel Interval Stabbing on the Automata Processor

Indranil Roy & Matt Grimm, Micron Technology, Inc., USA

Ankit Srivastava & Srinivas Aluru, Georgia Institute of Technology, USA

This paper investigates the use of the Automata Processor (AP) to accelerate applications that depend on comparing a single query element against a large unordered list of others. The comparison against each entry in the list is emulated as an automaton, and a large number of such automata can be executed in parallel on the processor. We have demonstrated these concepts by emulating interval stabbing queries on the processor. When the output processing does not become a bottleneck, up to 2.75 trillion comparisons of single-precision floating point numbers and 0.79 trillion comparisons of double-precision floating point numbers can be completed per second using the resources of a single PCIe-based AP-board. Our automata exemplify design techniques that maximize resource utilization and minimize performance bottlenecks which may be useful to future developers on this processor. Furthermore, these techniques can be extended to handle cases where different elements in the list can be expressed in a variety of formats, e.g. in the case of date stamps. Not only have we expanded the scope of the usage of this processor to floating point operations, but for the first time, demonstrated the same on the actual prototype hardware.

Accelerating Weeder: A DNA Motif Search Tool using the Micron Automata Processor

Qiong Wang, National University of Defense Technology, China

Mohamed El-Hadedy, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, USA

Ke Wang & Kevin Skadron, University of Virginia, USA

Motifs are the repeated patterns in a set of DNA sequences. Weeder is a software tool for the automatic discovery of conserved motifs in a set of DNA sequences. It falls into the motif enumeration family of motif discovery tools in which the occurrence of motifs in the query sequences are counted. Due to this feature, a function called oligo-scan which involves pattern matching becomes a bottleneck when dealing with large datasets. Micron's Automata Processor (AP), a massively parallel pattern matching processor, can significantly accelerate this stage. In our experiment, the AP-accelerated weeder achieves 676x speedup when compared to a single thread implementation on CPU.

What Have We Learned About Heterogeneous Supercomputing?

Wen-mei Hwu, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, USA

Since the introduction of CUDA in 2006, we have made tremendous progress in heterogeneous computing. We have built heterogeneous top supercomputers. Most of the top supercomputers in the world are heterogeneous computing systems. We have mass-produced heterogeneous mobile computing devices. New standards such as the Heterogeneous Systems Architecture (HSA) are emerging to facilitate software development. Much has been learned about algorithms, languages, compilers and hardware architecture in this movement. How hard is it to program these systems today? How will we program these systems in the future? How will heterogeneity in memory devices present further opportunities and challenges? What is the impact on long-term software engineering cost on applications? In this talk, I will go over the lessons learned from educating programmers and developing performance-critical libraries. I will then give a preview of the types of programming systems that will be needed to further reduce the software cost of heterogeneous computing.

Application Readiness for the Pre-Exascale HPC Phase

Stan Posey, NVIDIA Corporation, USA

Computational efficiency with increased demand on performance-per-energy-cost has become the overarching drivers behind architectural considerations for exascale HPC. The development of scientific and engineering application software that achieves full potential from future exascale systems will require a level of hardware-software co-design that is a relatively new approach for conventional HPC. The first pre-exascale systems announced under the U.S. Department of Energy CORAL program is designed with GPUs as a central component and technology enabler of co-design collaborations that will achieve accelerated application readiness for CORAL deployments in 2018.

This lecture examines the motivation and progress of GPU-based heterogeneous system architectures for the pre-exascale phase of HPC. The topics will introduce the requirements for extraction of fine-grain parallelism from HPC application software, and the current state of GPU acceleration for applied modelling and simulation with a review of the programming strategies deployed. Select examples are provided with relevance to science-scale HPC practice that quantifies the benefits of heterogeneous vs. CPU-only computing, including comparisons of performance and savings in power consumption.

Many-Core Approaches to Combinatorial Problems

Michael Krajecki, Julien Loiseau, Christophe Jaillet, François Alin & Arnaud Renard, University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne, CReSTIC, France

Combinatorics is a branch of mathematics concerning the study of finite or countable discrete structures. There are many combinatorial problems described in the literature such as the traveling salesman problem (TSP), the boolean SATisfiability problem (SAT) or the quadratic assignment problem (QAP), for which algebraic combinatorics techniques are widely used.

All these problems require a significant computational time to be solved whether using an incomplete or complete approach. While their complexity makes them good candidates for high performance computing, they also share properties that make them difficult to parallelize: randomized unpredictable memory accesses, inability to implement classic overlapping between data transfers and computation. Hence, many current HPC algorithms are only able to take scale up to a small number of CPUs.

In this talk, using a CPU implementation as a reference, we will introduce a many-core approach to solve the Langford problem on a large hybrid GPU HPC cluster. Our method is based on tiered model of parallelism using MPI, OpenMP and CUDA, exploiting both the computational power of standard CPUs and the NVIDIA GPUs. Tasks are being generated with a tree splitting method and distributed in a master-slave manner. Then, inside a hybrid cluster node, both CPU and GPU compute independently a part of the subtree. Because the GPUs handle about 60% to 80% of the computation effort, special attention is required at this specific point for a good balance. Using up to 258 CPUs and GPUs we break the limits of the Langford problem and solve the last open instance known as L(2,27) in the literature.

Elastic Stencil Code for Cloud-based GPU Spot Instances

Jun Zhou, Yan Zhang & Weng-Fai Wong, National University of Singapore, Singapore

This paper describes an elastic framework for distributed stencil computation on cloud-based GPU clusters. It uses pipelining to overlap the data movement with computation in the halo region and parallel data copy kernel within the GPUs. Instead of running stencil codes on traditional clusters and supercomputers, the computation is performed on the Amazon Web Service GPU cloud, and utilizes its spot instances to improve cost-efficiency. The implementation is based on a low-cost fault-tolerant mechanism that uses checkpointing, making it elastic so as to handle the possible termination of the spot instances. Coupled with a price bidding module, our stencil framework not only optimizes for performance but also for cost. Experimental results show that our framework outperforms the state-of-the-art solutions achieving a peak of 25 TFLOPS for 2-D decomposition running on 512 nodes. We also show that the use of spot instances yields good cost efficiency, increasing the average TFLOP/USD from 132 to 360.

